

Scientific Journals in Historical Perspective

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Abstract: This brief article synthesizes basic ideas that we must be familiar with when seeking to understand scientific journals. Firstly, it establishes when we can speak of scientific journals in the sense we understand today. Secondly, it initiates a response to explain the purpose of scientific journals. Lastly, it discusses the necessity of publishing our findings. This work is purely theoretical and aims to introduce the discussion.

Keywords: scientific journals; science; scientific communication.

Introduction

One of the tasks we will undertake today is to characterize scientific journals. However, if we were asked to define what they are and how they differ from other publications, would we be able to do so? To answer this question, let us trace the path they have followed to become the communication medium they are today.

Our journey begins in Europe 357 years ago. The earliest recorded instances of scientific journals, as we understand them today, date back to the year 1665. The first of these was published on January 5th of that year in France—*Journal des Sçavans*—followed by another on March 6th in England—*Philosophical Transaction*—(Reyna 2015; Piqueras 2007; Mendoza and Paravic 2006; Reyes 2018; Sabbatini 1999).

Understanding the context of this situation is crucial for comprehending the origins of scientific journals as we know them today. The Copernican Revolution, which commenced in 1543 with the publication of "*De revolutionibus orbium coelestium*" by Copernicus, marked the beginning of a new approach to understanding the physical world. In the ensuing decades, this novel perspective on addressing the problems of the physical world profoundly influenced various European intellectuals. Faced with a lack of critical methodology for established knowledge within universities, these intellectuals began gathering privately to discuss their ideas. A century later (Sabbatini 1999), no European university had officially adopted the innovative self-correcting methods offered by this new perspective, later known as the scientific method. Consequently, scientific societies began emerging in Western Europe.

These societies maintained a system of correspondence between their directors and various intellectuals who were members of the society or from other locations. These epistolary exchanges became increasingly widespread and critical. They were not only replied to but also discussed by other experts who added critiques, comments, and judgments to the work. This system was referred to as the "*Republique des Lettres*" (Sabbatini 1999; Echeverry-Bonilla 2007). As this system grew in scale and involved more participants, a medium was needed to facilitate the proper management of the interactions generated. This would become the seed of scientific journals.

As previously mentioned, the second half of the 17th century in Europe saw the establishment of scientific periodical publications as the ideal model for communicating new scientific knowledge. This is evident from the appearance of over a hundred such publications during this period. To name a few, *Giornale de' Letterati* (1668, in present-day Italy), *Miscellanea Curiosa* and *Acta Eruditorum* (1670

and 1682, respectively, in present-day Germany), *Journal des Nouvelles Découvertes sur Toutes les Parties de la Médecine* (1679, in France), and *Medicina Curiosa* (1684, in England) were founded (Mendoza and Paravic 2006; Piqueras 2007; Sabbatini 1999). These journals were characterized by their multidisciplinary nature, setting the trend for journals in general. Specialized journals would only emerge in the 19th century, driven by the field of medicine.

Officially, *The Lancet* (1823, in England) is the oldest medical journal in the world, although there are two journals claiming to be direct successors of earlier medical journals: the *New England Journal of Medicine* from 1812 and *The American Journal of Medical Sciences* from 1820 (Reyes 2018). A simple review reveals that since their inception, scientific journals have established themselves as the best and most prestigious means of disseminating new knowledge. Now, we ask ourselves: Did the same occur in America?

Scientific journals began arriving in our region at the end of the 18th and early 19th centuries, although their true consolidation only occurred in the last century. The traced antecedents demonstrate that the first scientific journal in all of the Americas, and also in the Spanish language, was *Mercurio Volante* (1772) in New Spain (primarily present-day Mexico). Other early American publications include *Medical Repository* (1797) in the United States, *Gaceta Médica* (1864) in Mexico, *Propagador das Ciências Médicas* (1827), *Semanário de Saúde Pública* (1831), *Diario de Saúde* (1835), *Revista Médica Fluminense* (1835), and *Revista Médica Brasileira* (1841) in Brazil, *Anales de la Universidad de Chile* (1843, still active), *Revista de Ciencias i Letras* (1857) in Chile, among others (Piqueras 2007; Mendoza and Paravic 2006).

The mentioned publications mostly belong to a bygone era, characterized by their general and diverse content. In the case of America, true scientific journals did not emerge until the 20th century, originating from universities. Thus, it is valid to argue that the true origin of scientific journals in the region lies in universities, and not in the 17th century as in Europe, where they were established by private entities. With this context in mind, we may ask: Does the origin of journals influence how we work with them? It is evident that the temporal and spatial context significantly shapes the processes, and the nature of American journals is no exception, as the public nature of universities has led to a similar inheritance by journals.

From their emergence in 1665 to the present day, there have been many changes in the way scientific journals are published. However, the underlying model's structure remains the same: a system in which a group of experts convenes to assess, comment on, provide feedback, criticize, and communicate new knowledge. Now that we have a general understanding of how scientific journals came to be, let us explore their specific functions.

The Purpose of Scientific Journals

In the eighth sense of the term "purpose" according to the Spanish Language Dictionary (DLE), we will utilize the term "sense" to denote "the reason for being, purpose, or justification of something." Thus, let us examine the purpose of a journal and understand when a publication fulfills its requirements.

Let us define what a scientific journal is. To achieve this, we can directly refer to existing definitions. For instance, the American Library Association (ALA) states that a scientific journal is a "periodical publication that publishes scientific articles and/or up-to-date information on research and development in a specific scientific field." The International Standardization Organization (ISO) mentions that scientific journals are "a serial publication that generally focuses on one or more specific subjects and contains general or scientific and technical information." (Aguirre 2006). The UNESCO comments that scientific journals, among other things, are those that provide "all the necessary details

to verify the validity of the author's reasoning or replicate their work" (Rovalo 2004). For our purposes, we will employ the definition coined by Latindex in its glossary, as it synthesizes the most widely accepted ideas about what constitutes such publications:

A journal that predominantly publishes research articles (derived from scientific research projects funded by public or private funds) or original studies that contribute to the discipline of the journal. They are required to apply a peer-review system for the approval of articles and tend to be highly specialized in their content.

Based on these definitions, we can propose a purpose for scientific journals, which would be:

1. To serve as a systematic record of knowledge and a repository for preserving it.
2. To serve as a fluid medium for communicating the latest advances in knowledge.
3. To ensure and certify the validity of knowledge.
4. To facilitate the construction and consolidation of scientific communities.
5. To provide public recognition of the intellectual property of those who generate new knowledge.

Now we understand that journals fulfill specific functions within the scientific community, as formal communication of new findings only occurs through their publication. This contributes to granting due recognition to researchers and ensures that the published work has been reviewed by a group of experts who agree that the study makes a valuable contribution. The cumulative tradition of science is reflected in the extensive archives provided by journals, which can be explored to expand our knowledge on specific topics. With this introduction to the world of scientific communication, let us discuss the question: Why publish?

The Need to Publish Our Findings

In this session, we have seen that European universities in the 17th century did not universally adopt, nor did they do so promptly, the epistemological changes arising from the Copernican Revolution. This period, spanning from the publication of Copernicus' "De revolutionibus orbium coelestium" in 1543 to Newton's "Philosophiæ naturalis principia mathematica" in 1687, marked the consolidation of a new way of engaging with knowledge. It involved discussion, criticism, and validation of established truths through a rigorous examination of each aspect. European scientific societies emerged as spaces for consolidating this scientific method and assumed the responsibility of formal scientific communication through periodical publications, which we now know as scientific journals.

Scientific societies were private groups associated with commercial enterprises, typically printing presses. Consequently, their publications were always part of private investment. When the mass sale of scientific journals transitioned from scientific societies to commercial publishers, largely as a result of the world wars, the privatization of scientific knowledge was not unfamiliar to Europe. From their inception, scientific journals had been private and access was restricted. In contrast, in America, scientific journals associated with scientific societies were sporadic and, for the most part, had short lifespans. The consistent and real emergence of journals in our region occurred in the 20th century, facilitated by universities. As a result, open access is the prevailing model for publications in the region, meaning they are freely available to both authors and readers. Only physical formats may involve costs, but in most cases, an exchange system (sharing the output of other universities) was established.

Given these historical and regional perspectives, let us discuss why we should publish. What are the benefits of publishing? What is the necessity of publishing in a time dominated by the internet and digital resources?

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